

1 ePOCT+ Rwanda: a clinical decision support algorithm for managing sick
2 children below 15 years of age in primary healthcare settings

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24 **Abstract**

25 Primary health systems in resource-constrained settings suffer from human resource
26 shortages, low quality care, and diagnostic uncertainty, resulting in over-reliance on
27 antibiotics, increasing risks of antimicrobial resistance. Digital clinical decision support
28 algorithms (CDSAs) help healthcare workers adhere to clinical guidelines and improve
29 prescribing practices. In this manuscript, we present the scope and content of 'ePOCT+
30 Rwanda', a CDSA trialed in primary health centers of Rusizi and Nyamasheke districts
31 during the DYNAMIC project. The algorithm is based on the WHO IMCI guidelines,
32 expanded to include a broader range of ages (between 1 day and 14 years) and acute
33 medical conditions encountered in primary care (57 diagnoses for young infants < 2
34 months and 144 diagnoses for children 2 months to 14 years). The digital application
35 used to deploy ePOCT+ prompts users to enter the results of medical history, physical
36 examinations, and laboratory tests to propose diagnoses, treatments and managements.
37 In addition to routine point-of-care tests, ePOCT+ utilizes haemoglobin and C-reactive
38 protein tests, as well as pulse oximetry, targeted to specific clinical conditions. We discuss
39 the rationale behind the content of the algorithm and the process of aligning it with the
40 Rwandan paediatric guidelines and tailoring it to the primary care setting.

41

42 **Keywords**

43 Clinical decision support, algorithm, primary care, CDSA, CDSS, clinical guidelines, child
44 health, digital health, Rwanda

45 Introduction

46 Human resource shortages are a significant challenge to health systems globally, and
47 especially in resource-constrained and remote primary care settings.^{1,2} In addition to the
48 overall low number of health workers, their educational background or level of medical
49 training is often insufficient for the services they are expected to provide.³ Clinical
50 guidelines, in theory, can help address some of these knowledge gaps. Guidelines
51 synthesize medical evidence into actionable information,⁴ and when adhered to, can
52 standardize patient management and improve quality of care^{5,6} by increasing evidence-
53 based practices. However, adherence to paper-based guidelines tends to be low,⁷ in part
54 due to their narrative nature and typical focus on a single condition,⁴ while patients often
55 present with multiple complaints. This requires simultaneous consideration of several
56 guidelines,⁸ which is difficult given high patient volumes, limited consultation time, and
57 sometimes conflicting advice. This combination of health worker shortages, clinical skills
58 and knowledge gaps, and non-adherence to clinical guidelines results in uncertainty in
59 diagnosing and treating patients, and subsequently low quality of services in primary care
60 settings. Over-prescription of antibiotics⁹⁻¹¹ is a key example of such uncertainty and low
61 service quality, contributing to the rise of antimicrobial resistance.¹²

62 With the recent advances in information and communication technology leading to
63 increased internet connectivity and decreased cost of electronic devices, governments
64 have embraced digital technologies to improve the quality of healthcare. In particular,
65 clinical decision support algorithms (CDSAs) have enabled complex integration of
66 multiple clinical guidelines into logical workflows that clinicians can follow through the
67 consultation. These tools have the potential to augment the quality of healthcare and help
68 narrow the existing gaps in human resources. The use of CDSAs has demonstrated
69 improved adherence to guidelines,¹³ better clinical outcomes,^{14,15} and in some cases
70 significant reduction in antibiotic prescriptions^{14,16} at the primary care level, especially if
71 the CDSAs integrate the use of point-of-care tests.^{17,18}

72 The goal of this manuscript is to describe the development and clinical content of a digital
73 CDSA called ePOCT+ (electronic Point-Of-Care Tests +) in Rwanda. The aim of the
74 algorithm is to improve the management of acutely ill children between 1 day and 15
75 years of age in the primary care setting, and particularly to decrease the unnecessary use
76 of antibiotics, without compromising clinical safety. Such antibiotic stewardship
77 interventions are essential in addressing the growing levels of antimicrobial resistance in
78 Rwanda.^{19,20} In addition to synthesizing clinical guidelines relevant to the pediatric age
79 group, the algorithm recommends targeted use of pulse oximetry, haemoglobin, and C-
80 reactive (CRP) point-of-care tests – currently not routinely used in pediatric primary care
81 in Rwanda – to improve patient classification and propose appropriate management.
82 Implementation of ePOCT+ is being evaluated in the health centers in the Western
83 province as part of the DYNAMIC research project.

84 Context and rationale

85 The DYNAMIC project introduced the digital CDSA in 32 primary health centers in Rusizi
86 and Nyamasheke districts. Healthcare workers providing care to acutely ill children were
87 trained in using the CDSA and pulse oximeters, along with a refresher on basic clinical
88 skills. Laboratory technicians were trained in measuring haemoglobin and CRP levels. All
89 children aged 1 day to 14 years seeking care at participating health centers for an acute
90 illness are deemed eligible and treated with the digital CDSA if written consent is provided
91 by their caregiver. The CDSA is deployed on an open-source tablet-based Android
92 application called *medAL-reader* (medical algorithm reader),²¹ with content available in
93 English and French. The sequence of questions in the application follows a logical
94 consultation workflow including patient demographics, basic measurements, medical
95 history, physical exams, laboratory tests, diagnosis, treatment and management, so that
96 the healthcare workers can use it step-by-step while consulting patients. Apart from using
97 the CDSA and point-of-care tests, consultations are done as usual. When required, pulse
98 oximetry is performed by the healthcare providers in the consultation room, whereas the
99 haemoglobin and CRP tests are done in the laboratory by trained technicians, as per
100 normal operation of the health centers. At the end of the consultation, the algorithm
101 proposes diagnoses, treatments, and managements, based on demographic and clinical
102 characteristics of the child and lab test results that have been entered in the application.
103 The proposed diagnoses and treatments can be accepted, rejected, or modified
104 according to the healthcare worker's clinical judgment. The target level of care for
105 ePOCT+ Rwanda is primary care facilities, and the target end-users are nurses with a
106 professional certificate of secondary education (A2), advanced diploma (A1) and
107 bachelor level (A0).²²

108 The algorithm is based on the WHO Integrated Management of Childhood Illness (IMCI)
109 guidelines,²³⁻²⁵ which is the standard of care for children under 5 years of age in Rwanda.
110 However, there are several important differences between IMCI and ePOCT+ Rwanda:
111 (1) ePOCT+ includes an extended age range from 1 day to 14 years; (2) the number of
112 diagnoses covered by the algorithm is also extended, while maintaining focus on acute
113 outpatient medical and surgical problems; and (3) ePOCT+ includes routine laboratory
114 tests recommended by IMCI and available in health centers (HIV and malaria rapid
115 diagnostic tests), tests not included in IMCI but available in health centers (urinalysis,
116 blood glucose level, stool microscopy, syphilis rapid diagnostic test), and some additional
117 devices (pulse oximeter) and point-of-care tests (haemoglobin, CRP) that are not
118 currently available or routinely used for children at the primary care level (i.e.,
119 haemoglobin is used mainly for pregnant women). Previous versions of digital IMCI-based
120 algorithms with¹⁴ and without²⁶ point-of-care tests have been validated in previous
121 research studies.

122 The rationale for extending the age range of the algorithm is to standardize clinical care
123 for older children and young adolescents, who are often not the focus of international and

124 national guidelines in low-resource settings. Lack of focus on this older age group in
125 health policies and interventions has resulted in a slower decrease in their morbidity and
126 mortality levels compared to children under 5 years.²⁷ Further, in prior studies, healthcare
127 workers have expressed frustration about not having access to comprehensive
128 information to treat the full range of health conditions they encountered²⁸ (the focus of
129 IMCI being on diseases with high mortality rather than those that are minor but still very
130 frequent). Therefore, we extended the scope of the algorithm to support healthcare
131 workers in providing evidence-based care for children presenting with additional non-
132 IMCI conditions, streamlining their workflow and making the tool more relevant to their
133 practice.²⁹ Lastly, we incorporated pulse oximetry and the haemoglobin test to improve
134 the identification of children at risk for developing severe disease, as well as the CRP test
135 to help differentiate between bacterial and viral infections and better guide in prescribing
136 antibiotics.

137 **Algorithm development and adaptation**

138 The starting point for developing ePOCT+ was an IMCI-based algorithm for managing
139 children between 2 months and 5 years called ePOCT, developed and tested in a
140 previous study in Tanzania.¹⁴ Content for managing sick young infants (below 2 months)
141 and older children (5-14 years) was subsequently added, while also expanding the list of
142 conditions for the IMCI age group (2-59 months). Criteria considered when expanding
143 the scope of the algorithm were: 1) prevalence of syndromes/diseases; 2) burden of
144 associated morbidity, mortality, and outbreak potential; 3) capacity to diagnose and
145 manage at the primary care level; and 4) existing evidence-based guidelines on
146 assessment and management. The detailed approach and process to developing the
147 expanded content of ePOCT+ is described elsewhere.³⁰

148 The content of ePOCT+ was then adapted to the Rwandan setting based on the local
149 disease prevalence, relevant national clinical guidelines and lists of essential medicines,
150 ^{25,31-44} and the actual availability of medicines at the health center level (Figure 1). The
151 DYNAMIC project clinical team reviewed relevant national guidelines and adapted the
152 algorithm accordingly. The adapted algorithm was reviewed by a Rwandan neonatal
153 expert for young infants (< 2 months) and an expert clinical group of five Rwandan
154 paediatricians for other children (2 months to 14 years). Feedback was solicited one-on-
155 one from each expert, including general feedback upon their review of the full algorithm
156 content, and specific feedback in response to a list of questions posed by the project
157 clinical team. Where the opinions of experts differed, a modified Delphi method was used
158 to gain consensus. A final group meeting was held, in which the various opinions were
159 presented and discussed, and whenever a consensus had not been achieved, an
160 anonymous majority vote took place. Upon revision of the algorithm, study clinicians
161 programmed its content in the *medAL-creator* software (a code-free drag-and-drop
162 interface to design algorithms).²¹ The algorithm was then deployed on tablets using the

163 complementary medAL-*reader* software²¹ and pilot-tested in a health center (Figure 1).
 164 The final algorithm was released upon further minor modifications following piloting. Of
 165 note, minor modifications continued throughout the implementation process (and are still
 166 ongoing); this manuscript presents the algorithm that was in use during the DYNAMIC
 167 research project.

168
 169 **Figure 1:** Overview of the algorithm adaptation process. Adaptation was done iteratively
 170 with revisions to the algorithm at every step before and after the Delphi process. Icons
 171 were obtained from the Noun Project (CC BY 3.0) <https://thenounproject.com> and
 172 <https://healthicons.org>.

173 **Algorithm content**

174 The ePOCT+ algorithm in Rwanda includes a total of 57 diagnoses for young infants (< 2
 175 months) and 144 diagnoses for other children (2 months to 14 years) (Table 1). When
 176 health workers use the medAL-*reader* application containing ePOCT+, they are guided

177 through a comprehensive clinical consultation. Questions and assessments depend on
178 the child's age and clinical presentation (Figure 2). Some questions and assessments are
179 prompted for all children or young infants within a respective age group according to IMCI
180 (i.e., systematic assessment for danger signs and other signs of severe illness, basic
181 measurements to assess malnutrition status, among others). In young infants, these
182 relate to severe and local infections, feeding and weight problems, jaundice, diarrhea,
183 and HIV risk and status,²⁴ and for older children, to common complaints of fever, cough
184 and difficult breathing, diarrhea, and ear problems, as well as assessment of chronic
185 conditions, jaundice, palmar/conjunctival pallor, and screening for HIV and TB.²³

186 Additional assessments relate to the main complaint categories as reported by caregivers
187 (Figure 2), which serve as entry points into diagnostic decision trees, and subsequently
188 lead to specific diagnoses and corresponding treatment and management plans (Annex).
189 The rationale¹⁴ and diagnostic algorithms in which point-of-care tests are used are
190 provided in Table 2.

191

192 **Figure 2:** Consultation flow of ePOCT+ in the medAL-reader digital application.

193 **Table 1:** List of diagnoses included in the ePOCT+ algorithm. Bolded diagnoses are not present in the 2020 edition of the Rwanda IMCI
 194 guidelines.²⁵

Category	Diagnoses	
	Young infants (< 2 months)	Older children (2 months – 14 years)
General / Fever	Critical illness, Severe clinical infection, Feeding problems [Lactation/ Lack of weight gain /Insufficient feeds/Lack of exclusive breastfeeding/Mixed feeding in infants with HIV positive mother], [Very low/Low] weight for age, [Physiological/ Prolonged /Severe] jaundice, Confirmed HIV infection, HIV [Exposed/Unknown/Unlikely], Incomplete vaccination	Simple febrile convulsion, CNS danger sign, Very severe febrile disease, Prolonged fever, Complicated prolonged fever, Typhoid fever , [Severe/Uncomplicated/Suspected/Severe suspected] malaria, Fever without source: presumed [viral/bacterial] , [Mild-moderate/Severe] anaemia, [Complicated/Uncomplicated] severe acute malnutrition, Moderate malnutrition, HIV [Exposed/Possible/Negative/Test unavailable], HIV positive mother, Hypoglycemia, Hyperglycemia , Known [sickle cell disease/cerebral palsy/congenital heart disease/HIV] , Prevention and screening
Respiratory	Pneumonia, Severe pneumonia, Respiratory tract infection	[Severe/ Bacterial/Viral] pneumonia, [Severe/Mild] croup, Common cold, Reactive airway disease, Suspicion of foreign object in airways, Hemoptysis , Suspicion of tuberculosis
Digestive	Diarrhea with [no/some/severe] dehydration, Persistent diarrhea, Dysentery, Severe abdominal problem Uncomplicated vomiting	[Severe/Some] dehydration, Acute diarrhea, Dysentery, Persisting dysentery , Persistent diarrhea, Severe persistent diarrhea, [Severe/Non-severe] abdominal condition, Constipation, Loss of appetite, Oxyuriasis, Intestinal parasitic infection: [protozoa/nematode]
Genitourinary	--	Lower urinary tract infection (cystitis), Pyelonephritis, Persisting pyelonephritis, Primary syphilis, Presumed primary syphilis, Presumed genital HSV, Urethral discharge syndrome, Inguinal bubo (lymphogranuloma venereum), Vulvovaginitis, Vaginal candidiasis, Vaginal discharge syndrome, Pelvic inflammatory disease, Dysmenorrhea, Pregnancy, Negative pregnancy test, Inguinal hernia, Balanitis, Suspected testicular torsion
Neurological	--	Non-severe headache , Suspicion of meningitis
Accident / musculoskeletal	[Uncomplicated/Complicated] Superficial wound, [Uncomplicated/Complicated] Deep wound, Birth-related soft tissue injury, Congenital muscular torticollis	[Uncomplicated/Complicated] Superficial wound, [Uncomplicated/Complicated] Deep wound, [Major/Minor] burn, Major trauma, [Major/Moderate/Minor] head injury, Confirmed fracture, Confirmed dislocation, Suspected fracture/dislocation, Confirmed clavicular fracture, Contusion, [Acute/Chronic] limp or joint pain, Osteomyelitis/septic arthritis, Carbon monoxide poisoning, Inhalation injury, Suspicion of poisoning, Uncomplicated suspicion of poisoning
Skin	[Severe/Local] skin infection, Omphalitis, Severe Omphalitis, Abscess, Cellulitis, Mastitis, Diaper rash, Heat rash, Scabies, Erythema toxicum, Mongolian spots, Transient neonatal pustular melanosis	[Complicated/Simple] abscess, [Complicated/Uncomplicated] cellulitis, [Complicated/Uncomplicated] impetigo, Folliculitis, Extensive folliculitis, Pediculosis, Scabies, Tinea capitis, Tinea corporis, Generalized tinea corporis, Pityriasis versicolor, Molluscum contagiosum, Non-specific viral rash, [Severe/Non-severe] measles, Scarlet fever, [Complicated/Uncomplicated] chickenpox, Eczema, Urticaria, Anaphylaxis, Diaper rash, Heat rash, Herpes labialis
Eye	Conjunctivitis, Neonatal conjunctivitis, Severe eye problem	Severe eye disease , [Bacterial/Viral/Allergic] conjunctivitis, [Preseptal/Orbital] cellulitis, Corneal abrasion
Ear, nose, throat, mouth	Acute otitis media, oral thrush	[Complicated/Uncomplicated] acute ear infection, Chronic ear infection, Mastoiditis, Foreign body in ear , [Bacterial/Viral] acute pharyngitis, Uncomplicated lymphadenopathy, Infectious lymphadenitis, Complicated neck mass, Mumps, Oral candidiasis, Oral aphthous ulcer, Tooth pain, Dental abscess
Malformation or birth anomaly	Concern for congenital syndrome, Concern for hydrocephalus, Concern for congenital heart disease, Minor anomaly, Cleft lip, Cleft palate/lip with high risk	--

195 **Table 2:** Point-of-care tests (POCTs) that are currently not included in IMCI but recommended by the ePOCT+ Rwanda algorithm.
 196 Diagnostic decision trees showing precisely how the results inform clinical decisions are shown in the Annex.

Test	Differential diagnoses by POCT (algorithms by age)	Type of test or assessment	Rationale for inclusion
CRP rapid test	1 month to < 2 months: Pneumonia vs. Respiratory tract infection (viral suspected). ≥ 2 months: Fever without source, presumed viral vs. bacterial cause; Febrile urinary tract infection (≥ 3 months to 2 years only if moderate CRP and positive urine dipstick); Pneumonia, viral vs. bacterial cause; Limp/joint pain vs. Osteomyelitis/Septic arthritis.	Semiquantitative immunochromatographic test that uses whole blood of a finger prick (categories of <10mg/L, 10-40mg/L, 40-80mg/L, 80mg/L and above); latter two categories signify a possible bacterial infection, except in some cases of young infants the threshold for bacterial infection is lower at 10-40 mg/L.	Symptoms and signs have been shown to be poor predictors of radiological pneumonia ⁴⁵⁻⁴⁷ . CRP can help better identify children with end-point pneumonia on a chest x-ray ^{48,49} or invasive bacterial pneumonia ⁵⁰⁻⁵² , as opposed to other types of pneumonia. The use of CRP during the initial diagnostic process in patients with acute respiratory infections has shown to reduce antibiotic prescriptions ^{53,54} . In the management of osteomyelitis and fever without source, CRP has shown to be useful in some studies ^{55,56} .
Hb rapid test	≥ 2 months: Severe vs. Moderate/Mild anaemia	Spectrophotometric measurement with a hemoglobinometer that uses whole blood of a finger prick.	Severe anaemia is a risk factor for mortality in children ⁵⁷⁻⁶¹ . No symptoms or signs allow to reliably detect (even severe) anaemia in children due to their poor sensitivity and specificity ⁶²⁻⁶⁴ .
Urine dipstick test	≥ 2 years to <15 years: Lower urinary tract infection vs. Vulvovaginitis vs. Pyelonephritis. ≥ 3 months to 2 yrs: Febrile urinary tract infection vs. Fever without source	Multiparameter urinalysis test strips that use middle stream urine.	The cause of fever without source in approximately 7% of children is a urinary tract infection (UTI) ^{65,66} . Management of febrile UTI requires targeted antibiotic treatment. UTI in infants and young children is difficult to diagnose clinically. A urine dipstick positive for leukocyte esterase or nitrite correlates with a high likelihood of a positive urine culture, whereas a dipstick negative for both helps to rule out UTI ⁶⁷ .
Pulse oximetry*	< 2 months: Performed in all YI; Critical illness or Concern for congenital heart disease ≥ 2 months: Severe pneumonia vs. Pneumonia	Non-invasive technique of measuring blood oxygen saturation and heart rate using an oximeter with age-appropriate finger/toe probe.	Hypoxaemia and tachycardia can be detected by pulse oximetry. Both signs are known predictors of severe infection ⁶⁸ and severe outcome ^{26,69-71} .

197 CRP: C-reactive protein; Hb: haemoglobin

198 * Pulse oximetry (if available) is recommended by the global 2014 IMCI version²³ for children with cough or difficult breathing, but not by the 2020 Rwanda IMCI
 199 version²⁵.

200

201 Conclusion

202 The goal of this manuscript was to describe the content of ePOCT+ Rwanda, a digital
203 clinical decision support algorithm to manage acutely ill children in outpatient primary care
204 settings. The aim of the algorithm, together with complementary point-of-care tests and
205 devices, is to improve adherence to evidence-based guidelines for assessment,
206 diagnosis, treatment and management of sick children, thereby improving quality of care
207 and decreasing inappropriate antibiotic use while ensuring clinical safety.

208 Due to the expanded scope of the algorithm, which includes many more clinical
209 syndromes and diagnoses than the IMCI guidelines, and the explicit incorporation of
210 management of multiple classifications/diagnoses, we expect that the uptake of the
211 algorithm and the overall acceptance of the digital tool will be high among healthcare
212 workers, resulting in superior adherence to clinical guidelines as compared to routine
213 care. However, completing all of the necessary steps during consultation is not sufficient
214 in and of itself; good clinical skills are still required in order to perform the assessments
215 accurately and enter reliable information into the tool⁷². The algorithm's recommendations
216 are only as good as the inputs entered by the clinicians along the way. Therefore,
217 particular attention should be paid to enhancing and supporting clinical skills of health
218 workers who use digital CDSAs⁷² through mentorship and supervision. Furthermore, the
219 option of accepting or rejecting the recommendation is given at the end of the
220 consultation, so that healthcare workers can still tailor their final decisions to the
221 practicalities and realities in the health centers (e.g., availability of medicines and referral
222 pathways). Healthcare workers must possess the necessary skills and knowledge to
223 accept the recommended course of treatment and management or to decide on
224 alternative options that are locally available and best suited to the patient's condition.

225 One advantage of digital CDSAs like ePOCT+ Rwanda is that they allow for clinical
226 content to be updated dynamically to account for new evidence or changes in guidelines
227 more quickly than printing and distributing paper-based documents. Continuous
228 adaptation is possible in accordance with evolving medical evidence, changing national
229 and international guidelines, and user feedback. The unique nature of *medAL-creator*
230 algorithm authoring software with a graphical drag-and-drop user interface puts the
231 adaptation process in the hands of experienced clinicians, rather than software
232 developers²¹. This makes the adaptation process efficient and transparent, so that
233 updating guidelines can be done in real-time, limiting the time-intensive and error-prone
234 clinical-IT interactions.

235 Potential limitations to the impact of ePOCT+ Rwanda are the varying levels of clinical
236 skills and digital literacy of healthcare workers and the need for re-training new staff on
237 the usage of the software and point-of-care tests due to a high staff turnover. These
238 challenges could be partly addressed through well-designed eLearning tools or through
239 integration of digital algorithms and related skills into the formal nursing curriculum.
240 Equally important to address are the healthcare providers' prescribing practices and the

241 caregivers' expectations around antibiotics, which both require additional education,
242 particularly in antimicrobial stewardship, regular monitoring and mentorship, as well as
243 national and local sensitization campaigns. Further to be considered is the interoperability
244 with other digital solutions used at the primary care level to avoid duplicative workflows.
245 These aspects, as well as costs, need for continuous support, monitoring and supervision,
246 and other implementation considerations are essential in planning for sustainable and
247 impactful implementation of digital CDSAs at scale.

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257 Author contributions

258 LC, RT, NV, KK, GAL developed the generic version of the ePOCT+ algorithm. VPR, LC,
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260 the algorithm to the Rwandan guidelines. VPR, LC, TD, AM, MN programmed and/or
261 updated the algorithm in *medAL-creator*. VvK and AVK drafted the manuscript. KK, FB,
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